

ENHANCING THE MASTERY SKILLS OF PUPIL - JOURNALISTS IN BASIC NEWS WRITING THROUGH (CEB) CONTEXTUALIZED ERROR – BASED WORKTEXT

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Abstract

This study aimed to enhance the mastery level of the campus journalists of Cuyo Central School, Division of Palawan in basic news writing through (CEB) Contextualized Error – Based Worktext. It used mixed methods, the quantitative approach was utilized to know the common errors committed by the participants of the study in writing news articles, their level of achievement and the testing of significant difference of their scores in pre-test and post – test. The challenges they met in utilizing the intervention material was also presented through quantitative method. The qualitative method was utilized in presenting the changes to be done to further enhance the material based from the challenges met by the participants of the study. Interview method and Focus Group Discussion were used as instruments. The common errors committed by the pupil-journalists in content is Following the correct news writing format or style that gained a score of 31.7, in technical Showing the news writers ability with a mean of 27.4, while in ethics most news writers did not cited sources properly and observed copyright laws with a mean of 7.6. There is a significant difference between the scores of pre-tests and post-test as revealed by paired-t test, a p-value of almost 0.00 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance moved the researcher to reject the null hypothesis. The great challenges that the respondents posted is No sufficient and concrete examples to create meaningful learning with a frequency score of 10 or 100%. The challenges they met were the bases of the enhanced intervention material. It can be concluded that CEB Worktext is effective as intervention material and the enhanced worktext as output of this study will be more appropriate as review material for campus journalists.

Keywords: *Journalism, Basic News Writing, Contextualized Error-based Worktext, Mastery Skills, Pupils Journalism Skills*

INTRODUCTION

Journalism is a form of writing, characterized by a direct presentation of facts or description of events without an attempt at interpretation, and designed for publication in a newspaper or magazines. Therefore, it is an art of telling a story concisely and simply as possible (Malinao, 2009). In the Philippines, the advancement of journalism starts in the campus, from elementary to college. Republic Act No. 7079, known as “Campus Journalism Act of 1991” strengthened its implementation. It declares the promotion and protection of the freedom of the press even in the school. It also molds positive values, enhances critical and creative thinking, and develops moral character and self-discipline of the Filipino youth. Based on RA 7079, the DepEd shall sponsor periodic competitions, press conferences and training seminar workshops focusing on historical and/or cultural interest in the country. Campus journalists and school paper advisers shall participate in this kind of endeavor either in school, divisional, regional or national levels from elementary to tertiary level.

The annual press conferences highlighted the different skills of every writer either in print, broadcast, or online media. Campus publication also signifies the academic excellence of every school in the country. The training and teaching on campus journalism to elementary pupils does not happen overnight. It entails a lot of coaching from their school paper advisers. According to Alkuino, a former school paper adviser, if you want to be a professional writer never stop writing for the wastebasket. There is no short cut way to victory in journalism. Many teachers who were assigned as school publication advisers are left to their resources without ample training in teaching journalism principles. There is no journalism elective in the Basic Education Curriculum, and most teachers rely on seasonal seminars sponsored by DepEd and non-government organizations. The school paper advisers may have to juggle the journalism training with the rest of their academic duties. They are facing a dilemma in the teaching and training of their pupil writers because of no formal education about journalism. No modules, workbooks and simplified theories preferably designed for an elementary pupil – journalists are provided that will help them sharpened the writing techniques of the amateur campus journalists. Through this, the researcher designed a simplified contextualized work text-based from the errors committed by his pupil – journalists. The worktext served as an intervention material to help enhance the mastery skills of the pupil – journalists in basic News Writing. News Writing is the main focus of this research which is one of the categories in the individual writing contest in the conduct of Division, Regional and National press conferences. According to Melvin Melcher, as cited by Malinao in his book *Journalism for Filipino*, the news is characterized as a break from the normal flow of events, an interruption in the unexpected. In the process of this research, campus journalists were given a news writing activity. It was evaluated and analyzed by the researcher with the helped of an expert (*winning campus paper advisers in the division, master teachers and university professors*) following the NSPC Score Sheet for judging news writing stated in DepEd Memo. No. 167, s. 2018. The errors committed by pupil journalists were the basis of the crafted CEB – Contextualized Error – Based Worktext. The crafted intervention material was utilized by the campus journalists. After answering the entire worktext, they were given another test to assess their mastery level in basic News Writing.

This research will help ease the burden of the school paper advisers who look for an intervention material that will help increase the writing abilities of their campus journalists. This will also promote the contextualization program of the K to 12 Basic Education Curriculum.

Background

Students continue to be interested in pursuing degrees in areas like news editing, photography, broadcast journalism, and various other kinds of mass communication, even as the media business continues to adapt to the technological world of today. Students still choose journalism as a major even if they may be aware of their future in a changing business. Social media has quickly risen to prominence in the lives of the vast majority of people, including journalists from all fields. Online material, most of which comes from social media platforms like Facebook and Twitter, has become more important to a number of media firms. There has been little research on how young journalism populations use the media and how they view both their journalism classes and the field itself, despite the fact that several studies have looked separately at technology and social media use and how students should learn in the current digital age. While the public may now get news from regular people thanks to the Internet and social media, the journalistic sector is still able to survive. The public prefers that journalists stick to the news and avoid overexposing the young population with entertainment tales, according to studies on what the sector should do to retain its consumers (Lewis, 2008). Today, students will study journalism in a way that is very definitely influenced by how

technology has revolutionized newsrooms. Since the publication of the first piece of written news in Europe in 1609, the journalism profession has seen a number of developments (Stephens, 1988). Even though they date back hundreds of years, early works of journalism nevertheless play a significant role in modern journalism practices. For instance, the development of mass media, which included the development of radio in the 1920s and the first CBS television broadcasts in 1941, were two crucial stepping-stones in the technical advancement of journalism. According to Stephens, the abundance of news sources may be unprecedented in human history. Stephens (1988) said that "the electronic media are barely entering maturity... Living in the late 20th century gives us the chance to see how various technologies compete to eliminate even the smallest flaws in our access to data. Computers have proven to be a big part of the technological revolution Stephens predicted, helping to process the enormous quantity of information and allowing users to be more selective in the material they consume. The phrase media convergence, which refers to the erasing of boundaries between media, and the notion that technology and social media usage has an impact on journalism, are relatively ancient concepts (Baran & Davis, 2009). Today's mass media is a prime example of convergence because of how social media and the spread of technology have merged many media forms. The newspaper business today includes digital content as well, including blogs, video, audio, interactive graphics, and information on social networking websites like Facebook and Twitter, in addition to traditional paper-based content. Technology advancements have made it possible for journalists to communicate with sources in a variety of creative ways and have empowered anybody with Internet connection to break news. Quinn (2005) asserts that "a shift in how individuals receive and engage with news is one result of the quest for convenience." One of the theories for media convergence is audience fragmentation. The public has a number of options for getting news, including conventional newspapers, broadcast media, radio, and most recently, the Internet. Media conglomerates like the Tribune Company control a variety of organizations, including newspapers, television stations, and websites, in reaction to convergence. Multimedia storytelling, including that of print, television, and mobile phone technologies, is another aspect of convergence. Additionally, convergence has produced multi-talented reporters who can write, edit, and shoot pictures. The multi-media journalist must be able to record and transmit digital data, according to Quinn (2005). The multi-media journalist may write for interactive media like the web, for the ear, for the eye, and for linear print periodicals.

Objective

This study enhanced the mastery level of the campus journalists of Cuyo Central School, Division of Palawan in basic news writing through (CEB) Contextualized Error – Based Worktext.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions.

1. What are the common errors committed by campus journalists in writing news articles as to the following indicators;
 - 1.1. Technical
 - 1.2. Content
 - 1.3. Ethics
2. What is the mastery level of the campus journalists in basic news writing using the contextualized worktext designed based from the errors they have committed?

3. Is there a significant difference between the mastery level of pupil journalists in news writing using the result of pre-test (*without intervention material*) and post – test (*with intervention material*)?
4. What are the challenges met by the campus journalists in basic news writing using the Contextualized Error-Based Worktext?
5. What changes can be made to enhance the CEB – Contextualized Error Based Worktext considering the challenges met by the campus journalists in using the material?

METHODS

Research Design

The study used mixed methods, the quantitative approach was utilized to know the common errors committed by the participants of the study in writing news articles, their level of achievement and the testing of significant difference of their scores in pre-test and post – test. The challenges they met in utilizing the intervention material was also presented through quantitative method. The qualitative method was utilized in presenting the changes to be done to further enhance the material based from the challenges met by the participants of the study.

Population and Sampling

The respondents of the study were the ten (10) pupil-journalists of Cuyo Central School, SY 2019 – 2020. The inquiry used purposive sampling method. The researcher selected ten (10) pupil- journalists who participated in the study.

Instrumentation

The result of the pre-test was the major source of the errors that served as basis in crafting the Contextualized Error Based Worktext while the result of post-tests revealed the mastery level of the pupil- journalists after utilizing the crafted intervention material. Researchers – Made – Open Ended Checklist was the major source of the researcher in identifying the challenges met by the respondents during the use of the material. Focus Group Discussion (FGD) and interview were utilized too to know more the challenges they met in the use of the material. These challenges served as basis of the researcher for further enhancements of the intervention material used.

Ethical Consideration

During the research process, certain protocols were followed. Necessary permission was sought from the principal of Cuyo Central School. Concerning the reliability and validity of the test and intervention materials, the researcher asked the helped of the professional experts, master teachers, university research professors and winning school paper advisers in the Division of Palawan.

Data Collection

The researcher conducted the pre-test, analyzed the results and crafted the worktext. The worktext was administered to the participants of this research. After using the said intervention material, they were given a post-test. The data were gathered, collated, tabulated and subjected for statistical treatment. The challenges encountered by the participants in using the intervention material were identified through Researchers- Made- Open Ended Checklist. It served as the basis of the researcher in enhancing the crafted material.

Data Analysis

The Descriptive Statistics involving the use of weighted mean and ranking were applied to know the level of mastery of the campus journalists in basic news writing and the common challenges they commonly met in utilizing the intervention material. To find the difference between the scores of pre and post-test T-test was utilized.

RESULTS and DISCUSSION

Table I. Common Errors Committed by Pupil Journalists in Basic News Writing and their Level of Mastery Before Utilizing the CEB

INDICATORS	Weighted Mean	Rank
N= 10		
A. TECHNICAL (40%)		
Show the news writers ability to organize information	27.4	1
Uses the lead that is clear and focus on the most important details	27.5	2.5
Uses transitions properly	27.5	2.5
Has clear and unbiased headline	28.2	4
Conforms with the principle of unity and coherence	28.4	5
Arrange details of events in decreasing importance	28.8	6.5
Avoids personal slants	28.8	6.5
Avoid the use of words with controversial elements or double meaning	29.3	8
Uses short and simple words	31.5	9
Observe the rule of grammar and syntax	31.6	10
B. CONTENT (50%)		
Follows the correct news writing format or style	31.7	1
Follow logical presentation of the event and emphasizes the most important or relevant facts	32.5	2
Present to the readers the most important details of the event	33.6	3
Uses appropriate lead type to get the reader’s attention	33.7	4
C. ETHICS (10%)		
Cites sources properly and observes copyright laws	7.6	1
Observes ethical and professional standards for journalism	7.7	2

(Fairness, relevance, accuracy and balance)

MEAN	69.43
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The Table I, shows the common errors committed by pupil journalists in basic news writing and the mean score of pre – test. For the common errors, *Shows the news writers ability to organize information* garnered a score of 27.4, which is the lowest score in Technical Area which composed of 40% of the total score. This indicator ranked 1 as common error committed by the respondents while *observing the rule of grammar and syntax* gained the highest score of 31.6 which ranked 10 as errors committed by the pupil journalists. In the Content which composes the 50% total score, *Following the correct news writing format or style* get the lowest points of 31.7 , it ranked 1 as common errors committed in the Content Area while most of the respondents has less error in *Uses appropriate lead type to get the reader’s attention* which gained the highest score of 33.7, which is ranked 4 as common errors committed in the content area of the news article. The remaining 10% is from the ethics, *cite sources properly and observes copyright laws* gained a score of 7.6 which is ranked 1 as error committed by the writer while the *Observing ethical and professional standards for journalism such as fairness, relevance, accuracy and balance* has a score of 7.7, posted as ranked 2 in the errors committed. The crafted Contextualized Error Based Worktext (CEB) was based from the errors commonly committed by the 10 pupil journalists as revealed by the table above. The Achievement or Mastery level of the ten pupil journalists in the Pre-Test is 69.43 as revealed by the mean score of participants of the study before utilizing the intervention material.

Table II. Achievement Level of Pupil – Journalists in Basic News Writing after Utilizing the CEB – Contextualized Error Based Worktext

INDICATORS	Percentage	Weighted Mean
N=10		
A. Technical (40%)	74.83 %	29.93
B. Content (50%)	67.8%	33.90
C. Ethics (10%)	82 %	8.20
MEAN		71.96

The Table II revealed the Achievement level of the pupil journalist after undergoing workshops utilizing the crafted intervention material (CEB- Contextualized Error Based Worktext). It shows the mean score of 71.96 in the post test conducted. It could be gleaned from the percentage of correct responses Ethics which is 82% excelled among the three areas followed by technical area which 74.83% correctly follows the technical rules of basic news writing, while the content is at the last ranked for only 67.8% followed the standards for content area of news writing.

Table III. The difference between the Achievement Level of the Pupil Journalists in Pre and Post Test Results

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Pretest	Posttest
Mean	69.425	71.96

Variance	36.80625	35.68266667
Observations	10	10
Pearson Correlation	0.996065018	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	9	
t Stat	-14.78651598	
P (T<=t) one -tail	6.38792E-08	
t Critical one – tail	1.8333112933	
P(T<=t) two tail	1.277758E-07	
t Critical two tail	2.262157163	

t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means	Pretest	Posttest
Mean	69.425	71.96
P-value (one tail)	6.39E-08	Reject Ho
P-value (two tail)	1.28E.07	Reject Ho
Interpretation	<i>There is a significant difference between the pretest and posttest.</i>	

The table above shows the paired t-test that was conducted between the pupil’s pretest and posttest. The mean of 69.425 for pretest and 71.96 for post -test. Furthermore, the paired t-test revealed a p-value of almost 0.00 at 0.05 and 0.01 level of significance. The researcher was moved to reject the null hypothesis which means that there is a significant difference between the pretest and post-test. It means that the increase in the mean of the posttest is significant and thus the material used is effective.

Table IV. Frequency Distribution and Ranking of the Challenges met by Pupil Journalists in Using the CEB – Contextualized Error Based Worktext

Common Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
N = 10			
Intervention Material (Content and Structure)			
No sufficient and concrete examples to create meaningful learning	10	100%	1
Inability to relate the lessons to actual life situations	9	90%	2
Unfamiliar Vocabulary Words	7	70%	4
Uncleared discussions of the least mastered indicators	7	70%	4
No effective motivation and introduction of the topic	7	70%	4

Does not link learning with prior experiences	6	60%	6
Methods of practice exercises are not suited to the needs and capabilities of the learners	5	50%	7.5
Not demonstrating in-depth knowledge of the subject matter	5	50%	7.5
Material does not encourage critical and creative thought	3	30%	9
Questions does not properly distribute to the different levels of learner's ability	3	30%	9
Overlooks to provide pupils with practice application of content learned	3	30%	9
Inappropriate font size and font style of the material	1	10%	12.5
Inappropriate localized examples	1	10%	12.5

Common Challenges	Frequency	Percentage	Rank
N = 10			
Implementation of the Intervention Material			
Teacher's/researcher's limited time intended for discussion of topics before the practice test	9	90%	1
Pupils' readiness in the use of the contextualized error based worktext	6	60%	2
Limited time allotted in utilizing the intervention material	4	40%	3

The Table IV reveals the challenges met by the pupil journalists in using the contextualized worktext. It can be gleaned in the content and structure of the intervention material, that all pupil - respondents considered **No Sufficient and concrete examples to create meaningful learning** as a challenged with a percentage of 100 and ranked 1. The 90% of the respondents are **enable to relate the lessons into actual life situations**. The 70% or ranked 4 of the pupils find difficulty in the **Unfamiliar vocabulary words, uncleared discussion of the least mastered indicators, and no effective motivation and introduction**. While only 1 or 10% of the respondents considered **inappropriate font size and style** and **inappropriate localized examples** as challenges as they utilized the Contextualized Worktext. In the implementation of the intervention material, **Teacher's/researcher's limited time intended for discussion of topics before the practice test** was ranked 1 or 90% of the pupil journalists considered this as a challenge, while **Limited Time allotment in the utilization of the intervention material** ranked last where only 4 or 40 % of the respondents considered this as challenge in in using the contextualized worktext.

What changes can be made to enhance the CEB- Contextualized Error Based Worktext considering the challenges meet by campus journalists in using the material?

Based from the challenges revealed by the respondents of this study, additional concrete examples will be added in the contextualized worktext to further enhance their skills in the least mastered indicators. Activities on relating to actual life situations will be added too, school activities or classroom experiences maybe employed as examples so that they can relate to the news stories that are used as examples in the worktext. Furthermore, examples maybe within the age level of the elementary journalists or within their level of understanding. Unfamiliar Vocabulary word will be unlocked at every indicator before the start of enhancement activities and motivation statements will be added for the pupil journalists to arouse their interest in using the contextualized worktext.

CONCLUSIONS

The findings of the study prove that utilizing contextualized intervention material based from their common errors is effective. From the findings, the following conclusions were drawn;

1. Majority of the pupil journalists cannot show a news writing ability to organize information while most of them can observe the rule of grammar and syntax.
2. In the content area of the news article majority of the pupil journalists cannot follow the correct news writing format or style while most of them can use appropriate lead type to get the readers' attention.
3. In journalism ethics, most news writers could not cite sources properly and observed copyright laws but they can observe ethical and professional standards for journalism (fairness, relevance, accuracy and balance).
4. The mean score of pupil journalists in writing news article in the post test is greater than the mean score of the pre-test.
5. There is a significant difference between the scores of pre-tests and post-test as tested through t-Test.
6. No sufficient and concrete examples to create meaningful learning is the common challenges met by the respondents in utilizing the contextualized worktext.
7. The challenges commonly encountered by pupil journalists in the implementation of the intervention material is Teacher's/researcher's limited time intended for discussions of topics before the practice test.
8. The change that may occur to enhance the intervention material are additional concrete examples, relate examples to actual life situations of the pupil journalists, unlocking of difficulties before practice exercise and motivational statements/activities prior to discussions and practice exercises.

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